

New energies, the last trump card of humanity for life

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Abstract

Recently, the use of new energies in the world has attracted a lot of attention; because it reduces the consumption of fossil fuels. The Middle East, with its rich oil and gas reserves, places the least importance on the development of clean energy, as it has the excuse that the cost of generating electricity from renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind, will be relatively high. However, in the long run, the damage caused by fossil fuels is in no way comparable to the cost of producing and using renewable energy!

This article aims to examine the existing capacities in the world for the use of renewable energy, to explain well that the production of energy from products such as oil and gas is very different compared to new energy and the need to change the trend. The current is felt.

Keywords: Renewable energy, environment, clean energy, fossil fuels, solar energy, wind energy-
